

Sales Prediction Using Machine Learning

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Abstract—Machine learning algorithms forecast the current output using historical data as input. Forecasts are prepared for the sales of the goods while numerous aspects are taken into account for a successful business. Here, the decision tree algorithm is used to estimate shop sales through sales prediction.. The main objective of every sales prediction is to maintain the profit and predict future demand and supply of the product. Using the correct sales prediction technique will assist the businessman in various areas of the business and will assist him in making a suitable decision. I used decision tree regression for sales prediction. The data set is taken from the Kaggle. Many industries are highly dependent on machine learning for sales prediction. Owing to its correctness. By using a machine learning algorithm, it predicts future sales that are likely to increase or decrease in sales. In this model Root Mean Square Error is used to evaluate the quality of a predicted model. And also use a Mean Absolute Error to measure the accuracy of a model.

Keywords—Decision Trees Regression, sales prediction, Machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

In order to predict or estimate current trends or factors that could have an impact on corporate policies or future financial, product, and marketing activities, sales forecasting is the process of investigating the economic, social, and financial aspects that control business activity. The entire firm relies heavily on sales forecasting. It affects the current and future plans of the business because the major income is generated through sales. There are so many sales prediction techniques available nowadays. Machine learning algorithms are used to predict sales trends since they are more accurate than earlier prediction methods.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study[1] examines the information gathered from a retail establishment and makes predictions about potential future store management tactics. It also analyses these effects and looks at how they affect sales because changing sequences of events, like as the weather, holidays, etc., can alter the state of different departments.

In this thesis[2] various different machine learning algorithmic techniques are used to obtain superior, optimal outcomes, which are then further analysed for the prediction problem. It has employed an ensemble technique, four algorithms, etc. Additionally, feature selection has been accomplished utilising a variety of strategies.

By using approaches like Clustering Models and measurements for sales forecasts, the goal of this article[3] is to obtain accurate findings for predicting future sales or demands of a corporation. The potential of the algorithmic methods is predicted and utilised appropriately in subsequent studies.

III. METHODOLOGY

Finding a machine learning model that will enable each organisation to keep a reasonable stock level is the aim of this project. Without any errors or doubts, this model can compute an appropriate stock level. The dataset is split into two parts: training and testing. To improve learning accuracy, the model should be trained with more data. To learn to forecast a suitable stock level in each store, the decision tree regressor will be utilized. The framework is in place.

Figure: methodology of Sales Prediction

The steps that require to be followed are:

1. Data Collection
2. Data preprocessing
3. Model building
4. Analyzing
5. Result

A. Data collection

Data collection is the process of gathering and analyzing information from a wide range of sources. To effectively use data to develop artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning solutions, data must be collected and stored in a way that makes sense for the particular business problem at hand.

B. Data preprocessing

This is the step that is done in every machine learning method. This process includes data cleaning, transformation, and data reduction. This all is done to make the data more effective. The data can be processed to make the data more effectively. The data can be processed to make our model more accurate.

Cleaning data: First, the data is cleansed. Users are deleting unnecessary entries from there. The dataset can also be cleared of the noisy data.

Splitting Data: The data is first cleaned, and then it is divided into training and testing datasets. The model is then trained using the set of training data.

C. Machine learning

Machine learning is a branch of computer science and artificial intelligence (AI) that focuses on simulating human learning by using data and algorithms to improve the system's accuracy over time.

1.Label Encoding:

Label encoding is the process of transforming tags into a digital format so that machines can read them. The best way to mine these labels can then be decided by machine learning algorithms. For the structured dataset in supervised learning, this is a crucial preparation step.

2. Decision tree Regressor: Decision tree regression examines the features of an object and builds a pattern in the tree's structure to forecast data in the future and produce meaningful continuous output. The absence of discrete output, or output that cannot be simply described by a discrete, well-known set of numbers or values, is referred to as continuous output.

IV. BUILD MODEL

The primary step in the sales prediction process is model construction. The algorithm is used by the user while developing the model. The actions required are:

1. Import Libraries

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')
%matplotlib inline
```

2. Load dataset

```
df=pd.read_csv('BigMartSalesData.csv')
```

```
df.head()
```

Item_Fat_Content	Item_Identifier	Item_MRP	Item_Outlet_Sales	Item_Type	Item_Visibility	Item_Weight	Outlet_Establishment_Year	Outlet_Identifier	Outlet_Lc
Low Fat	FDA15	249.8092	3735.1380	Dairy	0.016047	9.30	1999	OUT049	
Regular	DRC01	49.2692	443.4228	Soft Drinks	0.019278	5.92	2009	OUT016	
Low Fat	FDM15	141.6180	2097.2700	Meat	0.016760	17.50	1999	OUT049	
Regular	FDM07	182.0960	732.3800	Fruits and Vegetables	0.000000	19.20	1999	OUT010	
Low Fat	NCD19	53.8614	994.7052	Household	0.000000	8.93	1987	OUT013	

3.Explore data.

```
In [4]: df.shape
```

```
Out[4]: (14204, 13)
```

```
In [5]: df.info()
```

```
<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>
RangeIndex: 14204 entries, 0 to 14203
Data columns (total 13 columns):
Item_Fat_Content      14204 non-null object
Item_Identifier       14204 non-null object
Item_MRP              14204 non-null float64
Item_Outlet_Sales    8523 non-null float64
Item_Type             14204 non-null object
Item_Visibility       14204 non-null float64
Item_Weight           11765 non-null float64
Outlet_Establishment_Year  14204 non-null int64
Outlet_Identifier     14204 non-null object
Outlet_Location_Type  14204 non-null object
Outlet_Size           10188 non-null object
Outlet_Type           14204 non-null object
source               14204 non-null object
dtypes: float64(4), int64(1), object(8)
memory usage: 1.4+ MB
```

4. Dataset Details

- Item_Identifier:** Unique product ID
- Item_Weight:** Weight of product
- Item_Fat_Content:** Whether the product is low fat or not
- Item_Visibility:** The % of total display area of all products in a store allocated to the particular product
- Item_Type:** The category to which the product belongs
- Item_MRP:** Maximum Retail Price (list price) of the product
- Outlet_Identifier:** Unique store ID
- Outlet_Establishment_Year:** The year in which store was established
- Outlet_Size:** The size of the store in terms of ground area covered
- Outlet_Location_Type:** The type of city in which the store is located
- Outlet_Type:** Whether the outlet is just a grocery store or some sort of supermarket
- Item_Outlet_Sales:** Sales of the product in the particular store. This is the outcome variable to be predicted.

5. Statistical Summary

```
In [6]: df.describe()
```

	Item_MRP	Item_Outlet_Sales	Item_Visibility	Item_Weight	Outlet_Establishment_Year
count	14204.000000	8523.000000	14204.000000	11765.000000	14204.000000
mean	141.004977	2181.288914	0.065953	12.792854	1997.830681
std	62.088938	1706.499616	0.051459	4.652502	8.371664
min	31.290000	33.290000	0.000000	4.555000	1985.000000
25%	94.012000	834.247400	0.027036	8.710000	1987.000000
50%	142.247000	1794.331000	0.054021	12.600000	1999.000000
75%	185.856800	3101.296400	0.094037	16.750000	2004.000000
max	266.889400	13086.964800	0.328391	21.350000	2009.000000

6.Check the missing values

```
In [8]: df.isnull().sum()
Out[8]: Item_Fat_Content      0
Item_Identifier          0
Item_MRP                 0
Item_Outlet_Sales       5681
Item_Type                0
Item_Visibility          0
Item_Weight             2439
Outlet_Establishment_Year 0
Outlet_Identifier        0
Outlet_Location_Type     0
Outlet_Size             4016
Outlet_Type              0
source                  0
dtype: int64
```

6. Handling missing values

```
In [9]: df['Item_Outlet_Sales'] = df['Item_Outlet_Sales'].fillna(df['Item_Outlet_Sales'].mean())
In [10]: df['Item_Weight'] = df['Item_Weight'].fillna(df['Item_Weight'].mean())
In [11]: df['Outlet_Size'].value_counts()
Out[11]: Medium    4655
Small    3988
High    1553
Name: Outlet_Size, dtype: int64
In [12]: df['Outlet_Size'] = df['Outlet_Size'].fillna('Medium')
In [13]: df.isnull().sum()
Out[13]: Item_Fat_Content      0
Item_Identifier          0
Item_MRP                 0
Item_Outlet_Sales       0
Item_Type                0
Item_Visibility          0
Item_Weight             0
Outlet_Establishment_Year 0
Outlet_Identifier        0
Outlet_Location_Type     0
Outlet_Size             0
Outlet_Type              0
source                  0
dtype: int64
```

8. Combine Item Type

```
In [14]: df['Item_Identifier'].value_counts()
Out[14]: FDP03    10
FDN21    10
FDJ41    10
FDC41    10
FDT31    10
FDJ26    10
FDS33    10
NCF54    10
FDY24    10
FDP21    10
In [15]: df['Item_Type_Combined'] = df['Item_Identifier'].apply(lambda x: x[0:2])
df['Item_Type_Combined'] = df['Item_Type_Combined'].map({'FD': 'Food', 'NC': 'Non-Consumable', 'DR': 'Drinks'})
df['Item_Type_Combined'].value_counts()
Out[15]: Food    10201
Non-Consumable    2686
Drinks    1317
Name: Item_Type_Combined, dtype: int64
```

9. Data Visualization

```
Heat map for determining correlation
In [16]: corr_matrix=df.corr()
sns.heatmap(corr_matrix,annot=True)
plt.show()
Item_MRP      1      0.44  -0.0564  0.033  0.00014
Item_Outlet_Sales 0.44      1      -0.1  0.0086  -0.038
Item_Visibility -0.0564  -0.1      1      -0.014  -0.084
Item_Weight     0.033  0.0086  -0.014      1      0.00046
Outlet_Establishment_Year 0.00014  -0.038  -0.084  0.00046      1
```

a) Count of each Outlet_Type

```
In [17]: sns.countplot(df['Outlet_Type'])
plt.xticks(rotation=45)
plt.show()
Outlet_Type
Supermarket Type1 8000
Supermarket Type2 2000
Grocery Store 2000
Supermarket Type3 2000
```

b) No. of items with each type of fat content

```
In [18]: sns.countplot(df['Item_Fat_Content'])
plt.xticks(rotation=45)
plt.show()
Item_Fat_Content
Low Fat 8000
Regular 5000
Low Fat 1000
LF 1000
reg 1000
```

c) Count of different Item_Type

```
In [19]: sns.countplot(df['Item_Type'])
plt.xticks(rotation=90)
plt.show()
Item_Type
Dairy 1200
Soft Drinks 750
Meat 750
Fruits and Vegetables 2000
Household 1500
Baking Goods 1100
Snack Foods 1900
Frozen Foods 1400
Breakfast 250
Health and Hygiene 850
Hard Drinks 400
Canned 1100
Breads 450
Starchy Foods 350
Others 350
Seafood 150
```

d) No. of outlets of different sizes

```
In [20]: sns.countplot(df['Outlet_Size'])
plt.xticks(rotation=45)
plt.show()
Outlet_Size
Medium 8000
High 1500
Small 4000
```

e) No. of belonging to different categories of location type outlets

```
In [21]: sns.countplot(df['Outlet_Location_Type'])
plt.xticks(rotation=45)
plt.show()
Outlet_Location_Type
Tier 1 4000
Tier 3 5500
Tier 2 4500
```

f) Fat Content Vs Item Outlet Sales

g) Outlet Size Vs Item Outlet Sales

h) Outlet Type Vs Item Outlet Sales

10. Encoding categorical data

```
In [26]: from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder
le = LabelEncoder()
df['Outlet'] = le.fit_transform(df['Outlet_Identifier'])
var_mod = ['Item_Fat_Content', 'Outlet_Location_Type', 'Outlet_Size', 'Item_Type_Combined', 'Outlet_Type', 'Outlet']
le = LabelEncoder()
for i in var_mod:
    df[i] = le.fit_transform(df[i])

In [27]: df.head()

Out[27]:
```

Item_Fat_Content	Item_Identifier	Item_MRP	Item_Outlet_Sales	Item_Type	Item_Visibility	Item_Weight	Outlet_Establishment_Year	Outlet_Identifier	Outlet_Li
0	1	FDA15	249.8092	3735.1380	Dairy	0.016047	9.30	1999	OUT049
1	2	DRCO1	48.2692	443.4228	Soft Drinks	0.019278	5.92	2009	OUT018
2	1	FDN15	141.6180	2097.2700	Meat	0.016780	17.50	1999	OUT049
3	2	FDX07	182.0950	732.3800	Fruits and Vegetables	0.000000	19.20	1998	OUT010
4	1	NCD19	53.8614	994.7052	Household	0.000000	8.93	1987	OUT013

```
In [29]: df = pd.get_dummies(df, columns=['Item_Fat_Content', 'Outlet_Location_Type', 'Outlet_Size', 'Outlet_Type', 'Item_Type_Combined', 'Outlet'])
In [30]: df.head()
Out[30]:
```

Item_Identifier	Item_MRP	Item_Outlet_Sales	Item_Type	Item_Visibility	Item_Weight	Outlet_Establishment_Year	Outlet_Identifier	source	Item_Fat_Content_0	Item_Fat_Content_1	Item_Fat_Content_2
0	FDA15	249.8092	3735.1380	Dairy	0.016047	9.30	1999	OUT049	train	0	1
1	DRCO1	48.2692	443.4228	Soft Drinks	0.019278	5.92	2009	OUT018	train	0	0
2	FDN15	141.6180	2097.2700	Meat	0.016780	17.50	1999	OUT049	train	0	1
3	FDX07	182.0950	732.3800	Fruits and Vegetables	0.000000	19.20	1998	OUT010	train	0	0
4	NCD19	53.8614	994.7052	Household	0.000000	8.93	1987	OUT013	train	0	1

11. Drop Outlet_Establishment_Year, Item_Type

```
In [32]: df.drop(['Item_Type', 'Outlet_Establishment_Year'], axis=1, inplace=True)
In [33]: df.head()
Out[33]:
```

Item_Identifier	Item_MRP	Item_Outlet_Sales	Item_Visibility	Item_Weight	Outlet_Identifier	source	Item_Fat_Content_0	Item_Fat_Content_1	Item_Fat_Content_2
0	FDA15	249.8092	3735.1380	0.016047	9.30	OUT049	train	0	1
1	DRCO1	48.2692	443.4228	0.019278	5.92	OUT018	train	0	0
2	FDN15	141.6180	2097.2700	0.016780	17.50	OUT049	train	0	1
3	FDX07	182.0950	732.3800	0.000000	19.20	OUT010	train	0	0
4	NCD19	53.8614	994.7052	0.000000	8.93	OUT013	train	0	1

12. Splitting the dataset into training and testing dataset

```
In [34]: train_data = df.loc[df['source']=="train"]
test_data = df.loc[df['source']=="test"]
In [35]: train_data.head()
Out[35]:
```

Item_Identifier	Item_MRP	Item_Outlet_Sales	Item_Visibility	Item_Weight	Outlet_Identifier	source	Item_Fat_Content_0	Item_Fat_Content_1	Item_Fat_Content_2
0	FDA15	249.8092	3735.1380	0.016047	9.30	OUT049	train	0	1
1	DRCO1	48.2692	443.4228	0.019278	5.92	OUT018	train	0	0
2	FDN15	141.6180	2097.2700	0.016780	17.50	OUT049	train	0	1
3	FDX07	182.0950	732.3800	0.000000	19.20	OUT010	train	0	0
4	NCD19	53.8614	994.7052	0.000000	8.93	OUT013	train	0	1

```
In [36]: train_data.shape
Out[36]: (8523, 35)
In [37]: X_train=train_data.drop(['Item_Outlet_Sales', 'Outlet_Identifier', 'Item_Identifier', 'source'], axis=1)
y_train=train_data['Item_Outlet_Sales']
X_test=test_data.drop(['Item_Outlet_Sales', 'Outlet_Identifier', 'Item_Identifier', 'source'], axis=1)
y_test=test_data['Item_Outlet_Sales']
```

13. Decision Tree Regressor

```
In [38]: # Import Decision Tree Regressor
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeRegressor
In [39]: # Create Model
regressor = DecisionTreeRegressor(max_depth=15, min_samples_leaf=300)
In [40]: # Train the Model
regressor.fit(X_train, y_train)
Out[40]: DecisionTreeRegressor(criterion='mse', max_depth=15, max_features=None,
max_leaf_nodes=None, min_impurity_decrease=0.0,
min_impurity_split=None, min_samples_leaf=300,
min_samples_split=2, min_weight_fraction_leaf=0.0,
presort=False, random_state=None, splitter='best')
In [41]: # Predicting the test set results
y_pred = regressor.predict(X_test)
Out[41]: array([1673.98398729, 1349.51290433, 471.30684669, ..., 1892.06614452,
3805.94860417, 1349.51290433])
In [42]: # Cross Validation
from sklearn.model_selection import cross_val_score
cv_score = cross_val_score(regressor, X_train, y_train, cv=10)
Out[42]: array([0.5855529 , 0.57810651, 0.54307334, 0.58291815, 0.52136587,
0.56946275, 0.59113351, 0.56350217, 0.60017802, 0.54875222])
```

VI. RESULT

The results show the quantity of a particular item to be stored in a shop for a particular period of time The prediction's accuracy is indicated by the mean absolute error, while its quality is assessed by the root mean squared error. Using the decision tree regression we got 1084 mean absolute error, 1296 root mean squared error and also 0.58 R2 score.

```
R2 Score
In [43]: from sklearn import metrics
        from sklearn.metrics import r2_score
        r2_score(y_train, regressor.predict(x_train))
Out[43]: 0.5884050821570488

Mean Absolute Error
In [44]: print('Mean Absolute Error:', metrics.mean_absolute_error(y_test, y_pred))
Mean Absolute Error: 1084.6388358478663

Root Mean Squared Error
In [45]: print('Root Mean Squared Error:', np.sqrt(metrics.mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred)))
Root Mean Squared Error: 1296.1974448651208
```

VII. CONCLUSION

Using a decision tree regressor, this research proposes a new way to maintaining the appropriate quantity of items in a shop. We can determine an appropriate stock quantity using this technique. It assists the shopkeeper in maintaining a minimal stock level, allowing us to prevent wasting commodities or causing damage to items. This project offers a lot of potential in terms of future material purchases and raw material storage stock for a set amount of time, as well as logistic support.

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